

ISSN : 2321 - 2535

The Institute of Vision

SVIM

SVIM

e J o u r n a l

*of
Applied Management*

Bi-Annual Peer Reviewed e-Journal

VOLUME I

ISSUE II

NOVEMBER 2013

Shri VaishnavSM Institute of Management, Indore

(Approved by AICTE, Govt. of MP & Affiliated to DAVV, Indore & RGPV, Bhopal)
(UGC NAAC 'A' Grade Institute, ISO 9001:2008 certified)

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PRIVATIZATION AND ITS IMPACT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT THROUGH GLOBAL CORPORATE GOVERNANCE

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ABSTRACT

The debate over globalization is lively, often passionate, and has sometimes been violent. At least until recently, it has been intensifying. The debate is untidy and ill-defined., but we cannot afford to ignore it, for the views and attitudes expressed in it will inevitably affect public policy – and the issues are critically important for the future economic growth and well-being of people all the people of the globe.

Here is the message: Globalization – the ongoing process of greater interdependence among countries and their citizens – is complex and multifaceted. Many of the problems that the critics of globalization point to are real. Some of them relate to economics. Others relate to non-economic, but no less important, aspects of life.

Introduction:

Globalization poses four major challenges that will have to be addressed by governments, civil society, and other policy actors.

- One is to ensure that the benefits of globalization extend to all countries. That will certainly not happen automatically.
- The second is to deal with the fear that globalization leads to instability, which is particularly marked in the developing world.
- The third challenge is to address the very real fear in the industrial world that increased global competition will lead inexorably to a race to the bottom in wages, labor rights, employment practices, and the environment.
- And finally, globalization and all of the complicated problems related to it must not be used as excuses to avoid searching for new ways to cooperate in the overall interest of countries and people.

Good corporate governance practices instil in companies the essential vision, processes, and structures to make decisions that ensure longer-term sustainability. More than ever, we need companies that can be profitable as well as achieving environmental, social, and economic value for society.”

Boards, collectively and directors individually, are central in accomplishing these objectives, for, as Sir Adrian Cadbury said, “corporate governance is concerned with holding the balance between economic and social goals and between individual and communal goals. The impetus for this new understanding of board responsibilities can be found in a growing number of global and industry specific initiatives. Chief among these are the OECD Principles of Corporate Governance and the United Nations Global Compact. These benchmarks inform the work of the Global Corporate Governance Forum in its efforts to promote good corporate governance practices in emerging markets and low income countries

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About e-Journal

SVIM e- Journal of Applied Management is a Bi-annual, peer reviewed, Interdisciplinary Research Journal of Shri Vaishnav Institute of Management. SVIM focuses on integrating theory, research and practice in the area of management. It aspires to bring academicians and practitioners together.

SVIM e-journal is focused on contemporary issues in management and functional areas viz. Marketing, Finance, Human Resource, Production – Operations – Supply Chain Management, Information Technology, Corporate Strategy, International Business, Economics, Operations Research, Business Ethics & Corporate Governance and General Management. The e-journal invites Conceptual Articles, Empirical Research Papers, Case Studies, Book Reviews, and Summary of PhD Thesis, etc. Contributions rooted in the Indian/International context and reflecting the oriental ethos of management will be encouraged.

| Volume 5 | Issue II |

